

PERUSAL THE BASES OF HOLISTIC EDUCATION IN SRI SRI VIDYA MANDIR SCHOOL OF HENDALJURI, GHATSILA - A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The educational philosophy of Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, founder of The Art of Living, on which the Sri Sri Vidya Mandir Schools run all over India, is really unique which is related to the flow of enormous vigor and is infused with the paraphernalia to activate inner mechanism of learning through various co-curricular activities including meditation and yoga. The Art of Living (AoL) organization is trying to put across in a holistic outcome in students through such a system of education whose roots can be traced backed to the Vedic ages. In this study, after deriving the bases of holistic education afresh, the researcher tried to discover the bases of holistic education in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir school of Hendaljuri, Ghatsila. It was a qualitative study which was done mainly by observation and interview technique followed by rigorous content analysis. The study disclosed that the selected school is indeed nurturing as well as delivering the true holistic sense of education towards its tribal students.

KEYWORDS

Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School, Tribal Education, Holistic Education

INTRODUCTION- HOLISTIC EDUCATION

Holistic Education is more comprehensive and broad concept in the world of education. It is a development of new possibilities, experience and wisdom. Holistic Education has focused on creating new learners community who will be connected mentally with this planet. It has not focused on self but nurturing the students that they can reach beyond self realization. Then they can make relationship with larger community, nation, planet and the universe (Vengopal & Kumari, 2010). Encouraged by Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, Mr. Brij Chawla and a small team of volunteers started building schools in highly remote and unreachable tribal villages in Jharkhand in 1999. Today, Tribal School Project runs more than 30 schools which endow with free education, from kindergarten to High School; to over 4,000 tribal children in India. The aim of Sri Sri Vidya Mandir Schools is not only the academic excellence of the students but also all round development of them. They are also trying to provide them quality holistic education (“Seva Mandir Projects”, n.d.). It was a craving as well as an obligatory of the present researcher to explore first the bases of Holistic Education from the present existing literature and then tried to discover whether those bases of Holistic Education are really be retained in the Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School, Hendaljuri in Jharkhand or not. It was also crucial to ascertain the pledges made by the school to the public about the Holistic Education.

Gandikota (2008) investigated the relation between management style and growth of teachers and students of Rishi Valley School. Here the researcher used participant observation and perception survey as research tools. This study shows that in the management style of this school is supportive, contributively and non-authoritarian in some area. But on some certain situation there is an authoritarian approach. The teachers and students of this school are influenced by the management through directly or indirectly. The infrastructure of this school is very simple.

Grant (2017) conducted a study on holistic educational thought in K-12 schools. Here the researcher has tried to explain holistic educational thought on three basic principles. These are competitive eligibility, ecological literacy and lifelong optimal learning. According to the researcher holistic educational thought is a journey of beauty and enlighten. Here the researcher also offers a series of policy recommendations, testing and measurement, democratizing assessment performance measurement, testing and measurement. Dey (2017) analyzed on the influence of the organizational and management patterns of Maharishi Vidya Mandir schools on student's academic achievement. Here the researcher has used descriptive survey method. Statistical techniques are used for analyzing the data. This study is shown that Maharishi organization has played a pivotal role for learner's holistic educational development. Researcher has also found that like holistic development played an essential role for learner's academic achievement.

BASES OF HOLISTIC EDUCATION

The present researcher studied and triangulated the available literature extensively and concluded with the following dominant bases of holistic education. As per the essence of qualitative research, content analyses were followed thoroughly in deriving this. The requisite codes, including both open codes and in-vivo codes were generated for the bases of holistic education and from those codes the final bases were derived. The derived bases of holistic education are Community/Global Connectedness, Emotional Stability, Education on Democracy, Value based Learning, Peace Education, Learning of Social Responsibility, and Compassion/Empathy. In this study, the present researcher tried to explore and perusal these characteristics in respect to Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School at Hendaljuri, Ghatsila. .

RESEARCH QUESTION

How far the bases of Holistic Education are being followed in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To explore and perusal the bases of Holistic Education in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School

METHODOLOGY

The present researcher reviewed the existing related literature extensively and identified some of the characteristics or bases of holistic education afresh. As per the essence of qualitative research, content analyses were followed thoroughly. All the requisite characteristics or bases are analyzed as code including both open codes and in-vivo codes and from those codes some final bases were derived. The present study utilized the 'Critical Ethnographic Research' under Qualitative Research in which the Interview and Participant's Observation technique endeavours to study the Holistic Education in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School. With prior permission, interviews schedules were administered on both students and teachers with their preferred time. The whole conversations regarding each interview were recorded with their kind consent. Beside of this, the researcher also recorded her observations based on the observation schedule, regarding some selected overt behaviours of teachers and students in the school. The whole process was video recorded by the researcher, without hindering their privacy and natural setting. The investigator considered Content Analysis method for analysis of qualitative data (existing literature of holistic education, transcribed interview data of students and school teachers and data recovered from observations) for the present study. The collected data were processed, proper scoring was done and norms have been followed. Systematically checking, memoing, coding, enumerations and categorizing were done from the transcription data very minutely and effectively by the researcher with the help and advices from the experts in these fields.

FINDINGS

From the analyses of the entire transcribed interview data of teachers & students and the observed data observed extensively by the researcher herself in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School regarding the bases of Holistic Education, the following findings were revealed. Here eighteen categories are generated from the

interview data and some remarkable observation data were recorded by the researcher. The summary of the results both from interview data and observation data are presented here in the subsequent section.

Table 1: Corroborated Findings regarding the Exploration and Perusal the Bases of Holistic Education in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School		
Derived Bases of Holistic Education	Generated Categories from Interview Data	Generated Observation Data
Community/ Global Connectedness	Connection with the Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Different programmes are organized with cooperation & participation with nearby schools. ✚ Parent Teacher Association is there. ✚ Teachers maintain communication with every guardian in regular basis. ✚ School organizes social awareness programme in nearby villages ✚ School arranges excursion at colleges, universities and Ashram every year.
Emotional Stability	Emotional Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Students take midday meals in queue with patient. ✚ They help each others to take their meals. ✚ Teachers help students in stress. ✚ Teachers suggest techniques to overcome stress. ✚ Students like to face challenges. ✚ In problematic situation, teachers empathically help students to overcome.
	Mental Stability	
	Self Consciousness	
Education on Democracy	Participatory Democracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Class council & school council is very active. ✚ Election of class monitor is followed through democratic process. ✚ Students are familiar with the preamble of Indian Constitution. ✚ Learners express their opinion freely classes. ✚ School curriculum provides the notion of democracy.
	Good Citizenship	
	Freedom of Choice	
Value based Learning	Moral Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Practices of Prayer, Yoga & Pranayama. ✚ In daily prayer, famous quotations and spiritual dialects of educationists, philosophers, and spiritual gurus are read. ✚ Petite quiz questions are asked in morning assembly. ✚ News highlights are presented in morning assembly. ✚ The prayer is ended with the singing of National Anthem. ✚ Teachers & learners participate in religious occasions. ✚ Students follow school rules & regulations efficiently. ✚ Students are not in practice of telling lie. ✚ Student has habit of reading story books
	Escalation of Values	
	Character Building	

		and Classics.
Peace Education	Culture of Peace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Corporal punishments are prohibited. ✚ Teachers used to make them understand what they should do or should not do. ✚ If punishments rarely given, it is given in the form of academic activities. ✚ Students usually pursue the practice of self discipline. ✚ They quarrel quite naturally with each other but not too extensively. ✚ Teachers seldom intervene in resolving the quarrels. ✚ Bullying is totally absent.
	Self Help	
	Sustainable Outlook	
Learning of Social Responsibility	Social Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Learners feel that all religions are same. ✚ According to them, the basic beliefs of all religions are doing well for mankind. ✚ They take active participation in the social gatherings of all religions in school and also in the community. ✚ They help each others in every daily assignment. ✚ They gladly do their duty also. ✚ Teachers & students are concern for the environment. ✚ They organize environmental awareness programme with the active participation of nearby villagers. ✚ School organizes debates and discussions about environmental consciousness among students each year.
	Environment Cognizant	
Compassion/Empathy	Sensitiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✚ Teachers and students do their duties faithfully. ✚ They are very much loyal to their institution. It's like a <i>Mandir</i> to them. ✚ Students are dependent on their teachers for academic requirements and social & emotional supports. ✚ Teachers help their students in troublesome situation. ✚ Students used to share story books among them. ✚ In some special occasions, they share homemade special foodstuffs with their friends, irrespective of religions and creed.
	Judicious Notion	
	Empathetic	

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at the exploration of those bases of holistic education in the Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School of HendaJuri in Jharkhand. In exploring and perusal of these bases in that school, the present researcher interviewed as many as ten students and twelve teachers and simultaneously did normal as well as participatory observation of the school for near about eight months or so with obligatory breaks. It was found that the school maintains the community/province connectedness effectively with the limitation of global connectedness. Though global connectedness is the characteristic feature of holistic education but situating in the remote tribal belt of Jharkhand, according to the present researcher, it is quite problematic

for the school to be actively connected with the world or so. It was also found that a well balanced emotional stability is being maintained for students and teachers in the school. Through the observed and derived indications it can be believed also that the democratic practices or the education on democracy is generously imparting towards the students in this school. One of the most important bases of holistic education was found value based learning. It was observed that this component is being highly incorporated towards the students. An emblematic as well as relevant base of holistic education was found peace learning or peace education. Many of the literature emphasized the importance of peace in educational dome. Through some insignias, mentioned earlier, it can be assumed that the culture of peace education is cultivating in the school. Though the results signifies that quite a few of the characteristic features in learning social responsibility is lacking but some of them are also adequately observed in the school. The attribute compassion/empathy was also accounted through interviews as well as effectively observed in Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School by the researcher.

CONCLUSION

From the above study, by interpreting the data and coming to certain generalizations in the form of findings, it can be concluded that The Art of Living (AoL) organization is trying to put across in a holistic outcome in students through such a system of education whose roots can be traced backed to the Vedic ages. It can be said that the education system and especially schools have very important roles in raising a healthy society and qualified individuals. The school has the power to influence all other stakeholders of education. Such tradition when transmit to the students it can produce wonderful domino effect both in terms of academic achievement and holistic development of the students, which is the ultimate aim of a true education system. This study only tried to provide a verification of various bass of holistic education in the educational setting and helps us to understand how these bases in educational setting might encourage higher trust and better performance for the schools. Human responses are not only simply controlled by stimulus situation but he consciously controls his dynamic mechanism to reach his goals. A strong and useful communication process should be established between the school and the society. The school should be improved in terms of social and cultural aspects for an increased interest in the education system and for more positive attitudes for the society. In sum, this piece of research could have an impact on the field of educational research in India, and subsequently may be a step towards the enrichment of knowledge of holistic education, not only for India but also for other developing countries.

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